

(Original Research Article)

Title page;

Title: Will global climate change alter the temporal and spatial dispersals of the reservoir host Indian gerbil (*Tatera indica*) and zoonotic diseases spread?

Running Title: Distribution and habitat suitability of *Tatera indica*

Authors name and affiliations:

Kordiyeh Hamidi¹

¹Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad, Iran.

Tel: +989151098715

Saeed Mohammadi²

²Department of Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Natural Resources, University of Zabol, Zabol, Iran.

Naeimeh Eskandarzadeh³

³Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Razi University, Kermanshah, Iran.

E-mail: na.eskandarzadeh@gmail.com

Corresponding authors:

E-mail addresses: kordiyeh.hamidi@yahoo.com; kordiyeh.hamidiloyen@mail.um.ac.ir (K. Hamidi), smohammadi@uoz.ac.ir (S. Mohammadi).

Number of figures and tables:

Figure(s): 4 Table(s): 2

Conflict of interest:

The authors declare that they have no competing interest and have not a financial relationship with the organization that sponsored the research.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to H. Mozaffari, A. Hamidi and E. Ebrahimi for their kind supports and Dr. M. Nassirkhani for his critical review of the first draft of the manuscript. We also would like to thank Dr. J. Darvish at Rodentology Research Group, Department of Biology, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad for database authorization and access used as locality points since 2001 to 2011.

Will global climate change alter the temporal and spatial dispersals of the reservoir host Indian gerbil (*Tatera indica*) and zoonotic diseases spread?

ABSTRACT

Questions: How is the spatial distribution range of the Indian gerbil (*Tatera indica*), in response to the climatic variables in Iran? Can outbreak regions of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis, which is a great public health problem in many rural areas of Iran, be attributed to climatic variables that affect habitat suitability and distribution range of *T. indica* as one of the main reservoir hosts of leishmaniasis in both present and future?

Organism(s): The Indian gerbil, *Tatera indica* (Mammalia: Rodentia) which is belonged to the subfamily Gerbillinae.

Analytical methods: Maximum entropy modeling (MaxEnt) was used to predict suitable regions and the potential distribution of this gerbil in the present and future in Iran.

Results: Species distribution models showed that mean temperature of warmest quarter, precipitation of driest month, precipitation seasonality, and also mean temperature of wettest quarter were the most effective factors in the Indian gerbil occurrence. According to our model, southern parts of Iran were indicated as the most present suitable habitat for *T. indica*. The future distribution showed that suitable habitats for the Indian gerbil will increase considerably in Iran outwards to southwest, central and northeast. Consequently, cutaneous leishmaniasis will become an uncontrollable and most prevalent disease in preferred habitats of vectors.

Conclusions: These results will be useful for estimating the outbreak and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis as well as other infectious diseases which this gerbil play role as a carrier. Following a careful sanitation program, identifying the distribution pattern and monitoring population density of

the main reservoirs of leishmaniasis are of crucial concern for prevention of zoonoses emergence and development. Therefore, we recommend it should be determined an essential priority by centers for disease control within high-risk areas for current and future control program.

Keywords: Indian gerbil, Climate change, Ectoparasites, Species distribution projections, Leishmaniasis.

INTRODUCTION

All wildlife can carry pathogens (bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites) that cause infectious diseases in humans, called zoonotic diseases. In this regard, small mammals (mainly rodents) play a major role in the outbreak of zoonoses. Generally, mammals-reservoir zoonoses are various; they may be carried by arthropods (fleas, lice, mites, ticks, flies) or may show direct transmission from animals to humans (mainly in the case of pathogen of viral diseases such as Hantaviruses) (Smith, 2008; Montoya *et al.*, 2010).

In Iran, cutaneous and visceral leishmaniasis are among significant arthropod borne diseases. Zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ZCL) is a tropical disease caused by different species of the genus *Leishmania*. *Leishmania* is a Kinetoplastid (Order: Trypanosomatida) which is spread by sandflies of the genus *Phlebotomus* and *Lutzomyia* in the Old World and New World, respectively (de Vries *et al.*, 2015). Their primary hosts are vertebrates such as canids, rodents, and humans (Myler and Fasel, 2008). This pathogen which has widely occurrence in rodent's populations of savannah and arid regions, is also a great public health problem in many rural areas of Iran (Khoobdel *et al.*, 2003; Akhavan *et al.*, 2010). Several species of sandflies belonging to the genus *Phlebotomus* (Insecta; Diptera) such as *P. alexandri*, *P. ansarii*, *P. caucasicus*, *P. mongolensis*, *P.*

papatasi, and *P. salehi* act as vectors in transmission of ZCL between rodents. The most important parasite carried by these sandflies is *Leishmania major* (Yaghoobi-Ershadi and Akhavan, 1999; Yaghoobi-Ershadi *et al.*, 2005). A few wild rodent species are identified as the main species of ZCL reservoir hosts in Iran (Bates *et al.*, 2015). Members of the subfamily Gerbillinae (Mammalia; Rodentia) including jirds (mainly of the species *Meriones crassus*, *M. hurrianae*, and *M. libycus*) and gerbils (such as *Rhombomys opimus* and *Tatera indica*) are the main reservoir hosts of ZCL in Iran (Rassi *et al.*, 2001, 2006; Hepburn, 2003; Gramiccia and Gradoni, 2005; Gholamrezaei *et al.*, 2016). The Indian gerbil, *T. indica* shows a widespread distribution range in Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Turkey, Syria, Nepal, and Sri Lanka (Harrison and Bates, 1991). Lay (1967) reported this rodent for throughout the southern half of Iran. This serious pest species is locally abundant and also presumed to have a large population (Yiğit *et al.*, 2001). Indian gerbil is the principle reservoir rodent in the west borderline foci of ZCL (e.g. Khuzestan province: mainly in Dezful and Shush, and Ilam province), southern foci (south of Fars province) and southeastern foci (Sistan and Baluchestan: especially Chabahar) in Iran (Mohebbali *et al.*, 2004; Oshaghi *et al.*, 2009). The existence of numerous rodent burrows bears a high risk of contracting the disease. One of the major problems for the control and understanding this infectious disease is the lack of information about the distribution and dynamics of rodent reservoir populations. Transferring of pathogens between species (animals to humans and vice versa) and spreading zoonotic diseases to new areas simply occurs via moving the animals (reservoir, vector or carrier) from one place to another for example, for feeding or nesting (Ambu, 2014). Hence, each animal should be treated as a potential disease carrier since emergence and outbreak a new disease is always a possibility. Poorly developed conditions of some rural areas/ houses, weak health monitoring programs and inadequate information in detecting and dealing with the probable pathogen and infected animals, eliminating

them early, and also promptly preventing the outbreak of most pathogens make the zoonoses of great concern (Krauss *et al.*, 2003; Ambu, 2014). In spite of studies on ecological and biological peculiarities of this genus in Iran (e.g. Khajeh and Meshkani, 2010; Baramaki Yazdi *et al.*, 2011), very little information is available on the spatial distribution and the role of gerbilline rodents as reservoir hosts of ZCL (Khajeh *et al.*, 2017; Mohammadi *et al.*, 2017).

Distribution and ecological niche modeling is widely used as useful tool to predict potential ecological distribution range of any species and increasing our knowledge about its distribution and identify the habitats of undocumented diseases, and thus to anticipate the areas at high risk for disease occurrence (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2010; Karimi *et al.*, 2014). This is an accurate technique to select the most appropriate environmental variables to generate valid distribution models for species based on the idea that the known occurrence of an organism can be related to raster geographic datasets summarizing the factors that likely influence the suitability of the environment for the species across the occurrence landscapes (Phillips and Dudík, 2008; Elith and Leathwick, 2009). Therefore, we conducted species distribution modeling to predict the distribution range of abundant rodent *T. indica* and reveal the most important abiotic factors effecting the species distribution and assess the effects of future climate changes as well to obtain best results for estimating the outbreak and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis zoonotic diseases in Iran.

METHODS

Occurrence records and environmental data

For mapping the distribution range and habitat suitability of *T. indica*, presence data (georeferenced distribution records) of the species were assembled by field expeditions and using custom-made mesh live traps in North and South Khorasan provinces between the years 2017 and 2018, and also

museum records and available literature (Table 1). Nineteen bioclimatic variables as well as altitude with 30 arc-seconds (~1 km) resolution, obtained from the World Clim database (<http://www.worldclim.org/>). Environmental layers and records were applied by open Modeler v. 1.0.7 (de Souza Muñoz *et al.*, 2011) to determine the relevant grid values for each environmental layer. The extracted values were tested by SPSS v. 16.0 for checking the Pearson correlation coefficient. Layers with correlations lesser than 0.75 were chosen to run the final model.

Modeling of species distribution

MaxEnt (maximum entropy machine learning algorithm) v. 3.4.1k (Phillips *et al.*, 2017) was used to gain the final model with 15 replications. MaxEnt uses presence only records to represent high performance model prediction even with low occurrence data; it is accepted as the most efficient method of ecological niche modelling (Hernandez *et al.*, 2006; Phillips *et al.*, 2006; Elith *et al.*, 2011; Merow *et al.*, 2013). Finally, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) was considered as the criterion for the training data and acts as a measure for the model's discrimination ability to indicate present points from absent ones. The value of AUC is ranging between 0 to 1; a model with no detectability is expected to indicate an AUC of 0.5, an AUC greater than 0.5 indicates that the model is better than the random points, and a value closer to 1 indicates perfect accuracy of the model (Phillips and Dudik, 2008).

Climate data under the present and future change scenarios

To evaluate the potential future distribution of species for the year 2050 (average for 2046- 2065) the model was projected using MaxEnt (Morurta-Holme *et al.*, 2010). Global coupled Atmospheric-Ocean General Circulation Models (GCMs) are the different types of climate model used in

theoretical investigations of climatic change mechanisms (Covey *et al.*, 2003). By using GCMs from <http://www.ccafs-climate.org/>, we can not only simulate the present- day and project future climatic changes under different scenarios. We used the CCSM4 simulations for the fourth assessment report (AR4) in 44 CC scenarios to predict habitat suitability of species in Iran of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Pendergrass and Hartmann, 2012). All layers were downloaded in 30 arc-second resolutions and cropped for Iranian boundaries using ArcGIS v. 10.3. Based on different inputs of greenhouse gas emission drivers (i.e. population and economic growth, and technological choices), land use changes, environmental policy options, and adaptation processes (Solomon *et al.*, 2007), the IPCC recommended four representative concentration pathways (RCPs) (Miao *et al.*, 2014). The RCPs are consistent with a wide range of possible changes in future anthropogenic, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and aim to represent their atmospheric concentrations. We considered RCPs v. 2.6 and 6, which described a possible future range of energy state for the earth on the basis of different trends in climate change drivers. These threshold values for produced potential species distribution map were regrouped into classes of potential habitats with high potential (> 0.5) and low potential (< 0.005) (Abolmaali *et al.*, 2018).

RESULTS

With regards to the Pearson correlation coefficient seven layers were selected to run the model in MaxEnt. The ecological niche modelling outputs based on the model calibration results, for testing data was 0.7862 (with a standard division of 0.1032). The selected layers are presented in Table 2. Mean temperature of warmest quarter (percentage contribution value (PC): 54.12% and permutation importance value (PIMP): 7.92%), precipitation of driest month (PC: 13.90%, PIMP: 1.38%),

precipitation seasonality (PC: 10.02%, PIMP: 27.88%), and mean temperature of wettest quarter (PC: 9.53%, PIMP: 40.38%) had the most effect on the final model.

Results indicated that the most probability of presence of the species was in the environments with high temperature and low rainfall (Fig. 1). Based on the results, Khuzestan plain in SW Iran, coastal area of southeastern Iran, SE Dasht-e Kavir in Kerman province, as well as central and northeastern areas in Sistan and Baluchestan province were among the most suitable habitats for *T. indica* (Fig. 2). Potential distribution map of MaxEnt model by CCSM4 and RCP45 is shown in Fig. 3. Species distribution maps regarding to the potential distribution map of the Indian gerbil in the future represented remarkable expanding outwards of currently suitable areas for this host species with shifts into the southwest, central and northeast of the country. Future projections showed that south of Iran will be remained still suitable habitats for the species.

DISCUSSION

Species distribution patterns are among the most prominent issues in biodiversity management (Tittensor *et al.*, 2014). Distribution models have provided a new tool to explore diverse questions about species distributions (Nally and Fleishman, 2004). More specifically, investigating these patterns for host reservoirs species helps us to use it for public health program. In spite of increasing number of GIS based studies on the leishmaniasis vectors, especially wild rodent hosts, only few studies have been conducted in Iran (Ghatee *et al.*, 2013; Mollalo *et al.*, 2015; Fakhar *et al.*, 2017).

Zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis is an endemic zoonoses in many rural districts of Iran, and the Indian gerbils along with sandflies of the genus *Phlebotomus* play major role in transmission of the pathogenic agent (Mehrabani *et al.*, 2007; Ghatee *et al.*, 2017). Gholamrezaei *et al.* (2016) based on published literature showed more prevalent of *T. indica* was in southern and southwestern of Iran as

one of the main reservoir hosts. In the present study, output distribution map shows that the suitable habitat for *T. indica* is located in more southern parts of Iran. According to the response curves, increases in the value of rainfall and decreases in the temperature, will be resulted in the reduction of presence probability for this species, significantly (Fig. 1). Epidemiological researches have shown that temperature and precipitation affect the distribution of tick-borne diseases (Gage *et al.*, 2008). Recent studies have illustrated that the geographical distribution of vectors and reservoirs of leishmaniasis can be touched by environmental variables (weather parameters, vegetation and topography changes) (Patz *et al.*, 2006) and man-made disturbances (e.g. urbanization). Another effective factor in the distribution of *T. indica* is seasonality precipitation (coefficient of variation). This variable shows great variations in different months throughout the year, which is mainly due to the fact that these areas are located near the sea and show the coastal climate conditions; mild climate with hot summers and cool winters, high seasonal precipitation, and temperatures average in the 50 degrees (Islamic Republic of Iran Meteorological Organization Site, at <http://www.irimo.ir/>). In congruence with Molur *et al.* (2005), our results confirm that this species is found from the low altitudes in the south and center of Iran to the northern part of Iran, in a range of dry or arid habitats with sparse and low density of vegetation (Table 1). With coinciding the predicted distribution map resulted from this study with the map of biotopes of Iran, it is revealed that this species mainly prefers to inhabit in “hot dry desert”, “hot semi desert”, and “coastal dry” climatic zones (Islamic Republic of Iran Meteorological Organization Site, at <http://www.irimo.ir/>). The average altitude for the observed localities in this study is about 755 meter above sea level (a.s.l.) (with only two points above 2000 meter, maximum altitude around 2800 m a.s.l. and minimum value of 4 m a.s.l.). This gerbil as a warm area species, has penetrated Torbat-e Jam in the northeast of Iran (Razavi Khorasan province) (Darvish and Rastegar-Pouyani, 2012). A half century ago, this species was found in the

Tabas Region (South Khorasan province) as its northeastern most distribution range (Misonne, 1959). New data indicate that this species prefers to widely distribute towards northeastern parts of Iran, probably due to the effects of global warming and drought. The result of global climate changes in Iran led to increased attention to the impact of climate change on the incidence and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in different provinces of Iran (Alvar *et al.*, 2012; Mollalo *et al.*, 2015; Ramezankhani *et al.*, 2017). Climate change (CC) scenarios analysis helps us to predict future and get ready to face different predictable conditions and to better planning for prevention of disease prevalence. The future distribution showed that suitable habitats for the Indian gerbil will increase considerably in Iran outwards to southwest, central and northeast. The impact of climatic factors on the outbreak of leishmaniasis in west of Iran showed that there was a significant negative correlation between the temperature and diseases prevalence with highest incidence in October and November. However, no significant correlation was observed between the disease outbreak and rainfall or relative humidity (Yazdanpanah *et al.*, 2013). Similar study in Razavi Khorasan (NE Iran) showed that the maximum incidence of the disease was observed during the second half of the year (especially in the autumn; between October to December). Moreover, a weak positive correlation with relative humidity and rainfall, and a weak inverse correlation with sunshine and temperature were determined (Akbari *et al.*, 2014). However, Entezari and Eskandari (2014) showed that zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis had the highest incidence and prevalence in January and February in Fars province. Epidemiologically among bioclimatic factors, temperature and sunshine duration play a fundamental role in the transmission of vector-borne diseases, and showed direct relationship with the prevalence of the disease (Githeko *et al.*, 2000). Moreover, rainfall and relative humidity had inverse correlation. On the other hand, the impact of vegetation covers on the incidence of leishmaniasis and the life cycle of sandflies was studied in Yazd-Ardakan Plain. Comparing spatial

models of human disease with vegetation cover showed that the highest incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis was concentrated in areas with sparse and low density of vegetation (Mozaffari *et al.*, 2012). Bavia *et al.* (2005) showed similar results in correlation analysis between sandflies and vegetation density of mosquitoes in Brazil.

Generally, the Indian gerbils live in colony. They show overlap in external morphological characteristics with those of many species of *Meriones* (especially with the Sundevall's jird, *M. crassus* as coexistent rodent) which play role as alternative reservoirs for zoonotic diseases such as leishmaniasis (Fig. 4). The main diagnostic characters which distinct *T. indica* from other gerbilline rodents are including its tail color is dark above and below, but pale at the sides, sometimes slightly shorter than head and body length and hind foot sole is naked (Baramaki Yazdi *et al.*, 2011). Such great similarities in morphology and also the great overlap which can be found in the habitats of different species of jirds and gerbils, make some difficulties in identification or even misidentification of these species. These along with inadequate information about the ecology distribution of *T. indica* populations and its habitat structure (and also other gerbillines), are among factors which may result in difficulties in the studies of *Leishmania* outbreak and controlling programs for its reservoir hosts. However, study on the distribution pattern and monitoring population density of the main reservoirs of leishmaniasis in each area along with considering the vegetation cover which can provide a nest or shelter for the rodents in one hand, and also may effect on the biology and life cycle of the vectors on the other hand, are of crucial concern in zoonoses controlling and sanitation programs.

CONCLUSIONS

The Indian gerbil harbors several ectoparasites such as mites (e.g. *Dermanyssus americanus*, *Echinolaelaps echidninus*, *Haemolaelaps glasgowi*, *Laelaps nuttali* and *Ornithonyssus bacoti*), fleas (mainly *Xenopsylla buxtoni*), and lice species (such as *Polyplax gerbilli* and *Rhipicephalus* sp.) (Hanafi-Bojd *et al.*, 2007; Hamidi *et al.*, 2015; Hamidi *et al.*, 2016). Distribution range predication of this species as well as the role of bioclimatic factors in its presence will be valuable for preventing zoonoses and is important to control zoonotic arthropod-borne diseases programs. As it is seen in previous experiences, treating sicknesses (in humans or animals) is usually hard with waste of money and time. It is better to prevent an outbreak of a disease than to try to get rid of it once it has started (Oglesbee, 2011). Our results can be used to fill gaps in knowledge regarding the potential geographical distribution and optimal ecological conditions of *T. indica*. The results need further, more detailed investigation, especially by including molecular data, to provide an accurate understanding of the effects of global warming on this host and its ectoparasites species. For some of the zoonotic infections there are no vaccine and no specific drugs to treat. Hence, the efficient way to prevent zoonoses is achieved through careful attention to hygiene practices, follow a careful sanitation program and especially ways to avoid overcrowding of reservoirs such as rodents in high risk areas (Oglesbee, 2011).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to H. Mozaffari, A. Hamidi and E. Ebrahimi for their kind supports and Dr. M. Nassirkhani for his critical review of the first draft of the manuscript. We also would like to thank Dr. J. Darvish at Rodentology Research Group, Department of Biology, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad for database authorization and access used as locality points since 2001 to 2011.

REFERENCES

- Abdolmaali, S.M.R., Tarkesh, M. and Bashari, H. 2018. MaxEnt modeling for predicting suitable habitats and identifying the effects of climate change on a threatened species, *Daphne mucronata*, in central Iran. *Ecol Inform*, **43**: 116- 123.
- Akbari, E., Mayvaneh, F., Entezari, A.R. and Nazari, M. 2014. Survey of the role of bioclimatic factors in the outbreak of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *IJE*, **10 (3)**: 65- 74 [In Persian with English abstract].
- Akhavan, A.A., Yaghoobi-Ershadi, M.R., Khamesipour, A., Mirhendi, H., Alimohammadian, M.H., Rassi, Y., Arandian, M.H., Jafari, R., Abdoli, H., Shareghi, N., Ghanei, M. and Jalali-zand, N. 2010. Dynamics of leishmania infection rates in *Rhombomys opimus* (Rodentia: Gerbillinae) population of an endemic focus of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in Iran. *Bull. Soc. Pathol. Exot.*, **103**: 84- 89.
- Alvar, J., Vélez, ID., Bern, C., Herrero, M., Desjeux, P., Cano, J., Jannin, J., Boer, M. and WHO Leishmaniasis Control Team. 2012. Leishmaniasis worldwide and global estimates of its incidence. *PLoS One* **7 (5)**: e35671.
- Ambu, S. 2014. Rodents and disease- the never ending problem. *IeJSME*, **8 (1)**: 1- 2.
- Baramaki Yazdi, R., Shaghoozaie, M., Galdavi, S, Yousef Elahi, M., Shahriar Moghadam, M., Shokri Bousjein, N. and Javidkar, M. 2011. Identification of a new morphotype of the Indian gerbil, *Tatera indica* Hardwicke, 1807 (Muridae, Rodentia), from Iran. *Zool Middle East*. **52**: 111- 113.
- Bates, PA., Depaquit, J., Galati, E.A., Kamhawi, S., Maroli, M., McDowell, M.A., Picado, A., Ready, P.D., Salmón, O.D., Shaw, J.J., Traub-Cseko, Y.M. and Warburg, A. 2015. Recent advances in phlebotomine sand fly research related to leishmaniasis control. *Parasit Vectors* **8 (1)**: 131.

- Bavia, M.E. Carneiro, D.D., Gurgel Had, C., Madureira Filho, C. and Barbosa, M.G. 2005. Remote sensing and geographic information systems and risk of American visceral leishmaniasis in Bahia, Brazil. *Parassitologia*, **47**: 165- 169.
- Covey, C., AchutaRao, K.M., Cubasch, U., Jones, P., Lambert, S.J., Mann, M.E., Phillips, T.J. and Taylor, K.E. 2003. An overview of results from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project. *Glob. Planet. Change* **37**: 103- 133.
- Darvish, J. and Rastegar- Pouyani, E. 2012. Biodiversity conservation of reptiles and mammals in the Khorasan provinces, northeast of Iran. *PBioSci*, **2 (1)**: 95- 109.
- De Souza Muñoz, M.E., De Giovanni, R., De Siqueira, M.F., Sutton, T., Brewer, P., Pereira, R.S., Canhos, D.A.L. and Canhos, V.P. 2011. OpenModeller: a generic approach to species' potential distribution modelling. *GeoInformatica*, **15**: 111- 135.
- de Vries, H.J.C., Reedijk, S.H. and Schallig, H.D.F.H. 2015. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: recent developments in diagnosis and management. *Am J Clin Dermatol*. **16 (2)**: 99- 109.
- Elith, J. and Leathwick, J.R. 2009. Species distribution models: ecological explanation and prediction across space and time. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* **40**: 677- 697.
- Elith, J., Phillips, S. J., Hastie, T., Dudík, M., Chee, Y. E. and Yates, C. J. 2011. A statistical explanation of MaxEnt for ecologists. *Divers. Distributions* **17 (1)**: 43- 57.
- Entezari, M. and Eskandari, F. 2014. Relationship between climatic factors and the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Larestan city. *J Mil Med*, **16 (2)**: 99- 104 [In Persian with English abstract].
- Fakhar, M., Karamian, M., Ghatee, M.A., Taylor, W.R., Pazoki Ghohe, H. and Rasooli, S.A. 2017. Distribution pattern of anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis caused by *Leishmania tropica* in Western Afghanistan during 2013-2014. *Acta Trop.* **176**: 22- 28.

- Gage, K.L., Burkot, T.R., Eisen, R.J. and Hayes, E.B. 2008. Climate and vectorborne diseases. *Am J Prev Med.* **35 (5)**: 436- 450.
- Ghatee, M.A., Sharifi, I., Haghdoost, A.A., Kanannejad, Z., Taabody, Z., Hatam, G. and Abdollahipanah, A. 2013. Spatial correlations of population and ecological factors with distribution of visceral leishmaniasis cases in southwestern Iran. *J. Vector. Borne. Dis.* **50**: 179- 187.
- Ghatee, M.A., Haghdoost, A.A., Kooreshnia, F., Kanannejad, Z., Parisaie, Z., Karamian, M. and Moshfe, A. 2017. Role of environmental, climatic risk factors and livestock animals on the occurrence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in newly emerging focus in Iran. *J Infect Public Health* 2017 Dec 26. In Press.
- Gholamrezaei, M., Mohebali, M., Hanafi-Bojd, A.A., Sedaghat, M.M. and Shirzadi, M.R. 2016. Ecological niche modeling of main reservoir hosts of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in Iran. *Acta trop.* **160**: 44- 52.
- Githeko, A.K., Lindsay, S.W., Confalonieri, U.E. and Patz, J.A. 2000. Climate change and vector-borne diseases: a regional analysis. *Bull. World Health Organ.* **78 (9)**: 1136- 1147.
- Gonzalez, C., Wang, O., Strutz, S.E., Gonzalez-Salazar, C., Sanchez-Cordero, V. and Sarkar, S. 2010. Climate change and risk of Leishmaniasis in North America: predictions from ecological niche models of vector and reservoir species. *PLoS Neglect. Trop. Dis.* **4**: e585.
- Gramiccia, M. and Gradoni, L. 2005. The current status of zoonotic leishmaniasis and approaches to disease control. *Int J Parasitol*, **35**: 1169- 80.
- Hamidi, K., Nourani, L. and Moravvej, GH. 2015. The relationship of ectoparasite prevalence to the capturing season, locality and species of the murine rodent hosts in Iran. *PJA*, **4 (4)**: 409- 423.
- Hamidi, K., Nourani, L. and Moravvej, GH. 2016. New rodents' hosts of sucking lice, fleas (Insecta: Anoplura, Siphonaptera) and hard ticks (Acari: Ixodida) from Iran. *PJA*, **5 (1)**: 85- 88.

- Hanafi-Bojd, A.A., Shahi, M., Baghaili, M., Shayeghi, M., Razmand, N. and Pakari, A. 2007. A study on rodent ectoparasites in Bandar Abbas: the main economic southern seaport of Iran. *IAEH*, **4(3)**: 173– 176.
- Harrison, D.L. and Bates, P.J.J. 1991. The mammals of Arabia. 2nd edition. Harrison Zoological Museum (Sevenoaks), 345 pp.
- Hepburn, N.C. 2003. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: current and future management. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther.* **1 (4)**: 563– 70.
- Hernandez, P.A., Graham, C.H., Master, L.L. and Albert, D.L. 2006. The effect of sample size and species characteristics on performance of different species distribution modelling methods. *Ecography.* **29**: 773– 785.
- Karimi, A., Hanafi-Bojd, A.A., Yaghoobi-Ershadi, M.R., Akhavan, A.A. and Ghezalbashi, Z. 2014. Spatial and temporal distributions of phlebotomine sand flies (Diptera: Psychodidae), vectors of leishmaniasis, in Iran. *Acta Trop.* **132**: 131- 139.
- Khajeh, A. and Meshkani, J. 2010. A study of intraspecies variations of Indian Gerbil, *Tatera indica* Hardwicke, 1807 (Muridae, Rodentia) in eastern border of Iran. *Pak J Biol Sci.* **13 (2)**: 59- 65.
- Khajeh, A., Razmi, Gh. and Darvish, J. 2017. A study of ectoparasites in wild rodents of the Jaz Murian area in the southeast of Iran. *Asian Pac J Trop Dis.* **7(7)**: 418- 421.
- Khoobdel, M., Fajrak, H., Ladonni, H., Shayeghi, M. and Asadzadeh, R. 2003. A new method for military personnel protection against insects. *J Mil Med.*, **5 (2)**: 147- 155.
- Krauss, H., Weber, A., Appel, M., Enders, B., Isenburg, H.D., Schiefer, H.G., Slenczka, W., von Graevenitz, A. and Zahner, H. 2003. *Zoonoses: infectious diseases transmissible from animals to humans*. Washington DC, ASM Press, pp 214- 215.

- Lay, D.M. 1967. A study of the mammals of Iran resulting from the street expedition of 1962– 63. *Fieldiana: Zoology*, **54**: 1- 282.
- Mehrabani, D., Motazedian, M., Oryan, A., Asgari, Q., Hatam, G. and Karamian, M. 2007. A search for the rodent hosts of *Leishmania major* in the Larestan region of southern Iran: demonstration of the parasite in *Tatera indica* and *Gerbillus* sp., by microscopy, culture and PCR. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol*. **101 (4)**: 315– 22.
- Merow, C., Smith, M.J. and Silander Jr, J.A. 2013. A practical guide to MaxEnt for modeling species' distributions: what it does, and why inputs and settings matter. *Ecography*. **36 (10)**: 1058-1069.
- Miao, C., Duan, Q., Sun, Q., Huang, Y., Kong, D., Yang, T., Ye, A., Di, Z. and Gong, W. 2014. Assessment of CMIP5 climate models and projected temperature changes over Northern Eurasia. *Environ. Res. Lett* **9**: 055007.
- Misonne, X. 1959. *Zoogeography the mammifere de l'Iran*. Belgique. Institut Royal des Science Naturelles de Belgique. Memoires, deuxième série, fasc. 59, 160.
- Mohammadi, S., Vazirianzadeh, B., Fotouhi-Ardakani, R., Alae Novin, E., Amirkhani, A., Samii, J., Esamaeili Rastaghi, A.R. and Parvizi, P. 2017. *Tatera indica* (Rodentia: Muridae) as the prior concern and the main reservoir host of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis on the border of Iran and Iraq. *Jundishapur J.Microbiol*. **10 (1)**: e42452.
- Mohebbali, M., Javadian, E., Yaghoobi-Ershadi, M.R., Akhavan, A.A., Hajjaran, H. and Abaei, M.R. 2004. Characterization of leishmania infection in rodents from endemic areas of the Islamic Republic of Iran. *East Mediterr Health J.*, **10 (4- 5)**: 591- 9.

- Mollalo, A., Alimohammadi, A., Shirzadi, M.R. and Malek, M.R. 2015. Geographic information system- based analysis of the spatial and spatio-temporal distribution of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in Golestan Province, north-east of Iran. *Zoonoses. Public. Health.* **62**: 18– 28.
- Molur, S., Srinivasulu, C., Srinivasulu, B., Walker, S., Nameer, P.O. and Ravikumar, L. 2005. Status of South Asian non-volant small mammals: *Conservation Assessment and Management Plan (C.A.M.P.) Workshop Report.*
- Montoya, J.G., Boothroyd, J.C. and Kovacs, J.A. 2010. *Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's principles and practice of infectious diseases*, 7th Edition.
- Morueta-Holme, N., Fløjgaard, C. and Svenning, J.C. 2010. Climate change risks and conservation implications for a threatened small-range mammal species. *PLoS One.* **5 (4)**: e10360.
- Mozaffari, G.H., Bakhshizadeh, F. and Gheibi, M. 2012. Analysis relationship between vegetation cover and salak skin disease in Yazd-Ardakan Plain. *GEP*, **44 (4)**: 47- 50.
- Myler, P. and Fasel, N. 2008. *Leishmania: after the genome*. Caister Academic Press.
- Nally, R. and Fleishman, E. 2004. Influence of temporal scale of sampling on detection of relationships between invasive plants and the diversity patterns of plants and butterflies. *Conserv. Biol.* **18 (6)**: 1525- 1532.
- Oglesbee, B.L. 2011. *Blackwell's five-minute veterinary consult: small mammal*, Second Edition. John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- Oshaghi, M.A., Maleki Ravasan, N., Javadian, E., Mohebbali, M., Hajjaran, H., Zare, Z., Mohtarami, F. and Rassi, Y. 2009. Vector incrimination of sand flies in the most important visceral leishmaniasis focus in Iran. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* **81 (4)**: 572- 577.
- Patz, J.A. and Olson, S.H. 2006. Climate change and health: global to local influences on disease risk. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol.* **100**: 535- 549.

- Pendergrass, A.G. and Hatmann, D.L. 2012. Global-mean precipitation and black carbon in AR4 simulations. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **39** (1): L01703.
- Phillips, S.J., Anderson, R.P. and Schapire, R.E. 2006. Maximum entropy modelling of species geographic distributions. *Ecol Modell.* **190**: 231– 259.
- Phillips, S.J. and Dudík, M. 2008. Modeling of species distributions with Maxent: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation. *Ecography*, **31**: 161- 175.
- Phillips, S.J., Anderson, R.P., Dudík, M., Schapire, R.E. and Blair, M. 2017. Opening the black box: an open-source release of Maxent. *Ecography*, **40**: 887- 893.
- Ramezankhani, R., Sajjadi, N., Nezakati Esmailzadeh, R., Jozi, S.A. and Shirzadi, M.R. 2017. Spatial analysis of cutaneous leishmaniasis in an endemic area of Iran based on environmental factors. *Geospat Health.* **12** (2): 578.
- Rassi, Y., Jalali, M., Javadian, E. and Moatazedian, M.H. 2001. Confirmation of *Meriones libycus* (Rodentia: Gerbillidae) as the main reservoir host of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in Arsanjan, Fars Province, south of Iran (1999- 2000). *Iranian J Publ Health*, **30**: 143- 4.
- Rassi, Y., Javadian, E., Amin, M., Rafizadeh, S., Vatandoost, H. and Motazedian, H. 2006. *Meriones libycus* is the main reservoir zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in south Islamic Republic of Iran. *East Mediterr Health J*, **12**: 474- 7.
- Smith, V.S., Light, J.E. and Durden, L.A. 2008. Rodent louse diversity, phylogeny, and cospeciation in the Manu Biosphere Reserve, Peru. *Biol J Linn Soc*, **95**: 598- 610.
- Solomon, I.S., Qin, D., Manning, M., Chen, Z., Marquis, M., Averyt, K.B., Tignor, M. and Miller, H.L. 2007. Climate Change: The physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group 1 to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (pp. 1e18). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

- Tittensor, D.P., Walpole, M., Hill, S.L., Boyce, D.G., Britten, G.L., Burgess, N.D. and Baumung, R. 2014. A mid-term analysis of progress toward international biodiversity targets. *Science*. **346 (6206)**: 241– 244.
- Yaghoobi-Ershadi, M.R. and Akhavan, A.A. 1999. Entomological survey of sand flies (Diptera: Psychodidae) in a new focus of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniosis in Iran. *Acta Trop*, **73**: 321- 6.
- Yaghoobi-Ershadi, M.R., Akhavan, A.A., Zahraei-Ramazani, A.R., Jalali-Zand, A.R. and Piazak, N. 2005. Bionomics of *Phlebotomus papatasi* (Diptera: Psychodidae) in an endemic focus of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis in central Iran. *J Vector Ecol*, **30**: 115- 8.
- Yazdanpanah, H., Baratian, A. and Karimi, S. 2013. Study the relationship of the effective climatic factors on the outbreak of leishmaniasis in Qasr-e qand county. *Spatial Planing*, **3 (3)**: 69- 86 [in Persian].
- Yiğit, N., Colak, E., Verimli, R., Ozkurt, S. and Sozen, M. 2001. A study on the distribution morphology and karyology of *Tatera indica* (Hardwicke, 1807) (Mammalia: Rodentia) in Turkey. *Turk J Zool.*, **25**: 65- 67.

Table legends:

Table 1. Coordinate records for the Indian gerbil, *Tatera indica*, used in the present study. ZMFUM: Zoology Museum of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad. Data available on the web: GBIF at <https://www.gbif.org>, and VerNet at <http://www.vertnet.org>.

Year	Month	Day	Locality	Reference(s)
1420			Zabol, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
1349	3		Bojnord, North Khorasan	Author's unpublished data
1268			Bandar Abbas, Hormozgan	ZMFUM
1238	5		Birjand, South Khorasan	Author's unpublished data
1715	1		Forbat-e Jam, Razavi Khorasan	Shah and Rastegar- Pouyani, 2012
1747			Jiroft, Kerman	ZMFUM
1550			habahar, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
1099			Zabol, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
1326	3		Chenaran, Razavi Khorasan	ZMFUM
1139			Karkhe, Khuzestan	ZMFUM
1777	7		Nehbandan, South Khorasan	Author's unpublished data
1503			Zabol, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
1035	3		Fakhrabad, Yazd	ZMFUM
1755			Ar-e-qand, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
1591	2		Memarloo, Fars	ZMFUM
1596			Lara, Qeshm Island, Hormozgan	ZMFUM
1505	2		Mehriz, Yazd	ZMFUM
1094			Minab, Hormozgan	ZMFUM

77	4	5	oukabad, Sistan and Baluchestan	ZMFUM
09	6		Hoveyzeh, Khuzestan	ZMFUM
41	0	9	Yazd	ZMFUM
30	6	3	Rayen, Kerman	GBIF
71	4		Zabol, Sistan and Baluchestan	GBIF
05	8	9	Kerman	GBIF
40	7		Dezful, Khuzestan	GBIF
40	8		Dezful, Khuzestan	GBIF
08	9	3	Kerman	GBIF
51	8		Ramhormoz, Khuzestan	GBIF
55	2	7	Jahrom, Fars	GBIF
29	0		Ahram, Bushehr	GBIF
25	1		Shush, Khuzestan	GBIF
39	6		Fahraj, Kerman	GBIF
32	8		Zabol, Sistan and Baluchestan	GBIF
33	7		Ahwaz, Khuzestan	GBIF
55	1		aran, Kohgiluyeh and Boyer-Ahmad	GBIF
50	2		anshahr, Sistan and Baluchestan	GBIF
31	3	5	Pol-e Abginah, Fars	GBIF
47	9		Minab, Hormozgan	VertNet
53	8		Kazerun, Fars	VertNet

Table 2. Bioclimatic variables used to develop the distribution model in MaxEnt. Contribution ratio (%) and permutation importance value for each layer are also shown.

Variable	Contribution percentage value	Permutation importance (%)
Bio10 (mean temperature of warmest quarter)	54.12	7.92
Bio14 (precipitation of driest month)	13.90	1.38
Bio15 (precipitation seasonality; coefficient of variation)	10.02	27.88
Bio8 (mean temperature of wettest quarter)	9.53	40.38
Bio3 (isothermality)	5.36	3.14
Bio12 (annual precipitation)	4.27	8.64
Bio2 (mean diurnal range; mean of monthly [maximum temperature- minimum temperature])	2.79	10.67

Figure legends:

Fig. 1. The response curves of four variables with greatest effect on the model. A. Bio8: mean temperature of wettest quarter (in $^{\circ}\text{C} \times 10$); B. Bio10: mean temperature of warmest quarter (in $^{\circ}\text{C} \times 10$); C. Bio14: precipitation of driest month (in mm); D. Bio15: precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation) (%).

Fig. 2. Potential distribution map of the Indian gerbil *Tatera indica* and its classified map in the present. The locality points are shown in black circle.

Fig. 3. Potential distribution map of the Indian gerbil *Tatera indica* and its classified map in the future. The locality points are shown in black circle.

Fig. 4. A. Habitat and vegetation cover of the Indian gerbil (*Tatera indica*) and Sundevall's jird (*Meriones crassus*), two coexistent reservoir gerbilline rodents for leishmaniasis; Ferdows county, South Khorasan province, Iran. B. Burrow entries of a colony of *T. indica*; C. Comparison of external morphology of *T. indica* and *M. crassus*. The main diagnostic character to distinct first species from other gerbilline rodents is its bicolored tail (dark color above and below, pale at the sides).